

Effect of the Structural Changes and Donor Atoms on the Stabilities of some Binary Complexes of Lanthanone(III) Heterochelates in Aqueous Media, containing O^-O^- , $S-O^-$ and $N-O^-$ Donor Atoms and their Correlation

A. K. PATEL and J. D. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

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Binary heterochelates [ML], where M = lanthanone(III) ions and L = N, O and/or S containing donor atom ligands have been studied¹. It is found that lanthanone(III) ions play an important role in various biochemical reactions². The lanthanide metal complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 2-picolinic acid and catechol have been found to exhibit fungicidal properties³. The formation constants of trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Tb, Dy and Yb with glycylglycine have been determined using pH-metric method⁴. The equilibrium constants and thermodynamic parameters of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes with *N*-butylthioglycollate have also been studied⁵. La^{III} and Ce^{III} are known⁶ to form complexes with amino acids.

In present investigation systematic approach has been made to establish the effect of structural changes and donor atoms on formation constants of binary heterochelates of lanthanone(III) ions. The correlation for the stabilities of oxy, thio, amino acids and aromatic phenols is presented in Figs. 1-3.

Fig. 1. Correlation of stabilities of the ligands with lanthanones : (Δ) GA, (●) TGA, (Δ) glycine and (▲) catechol.

Fig. 2. Correlation of stabilities of the ligands with lanthanones : (●) LA, (Δ) TLA, (▲) α -alanine and (O) pyrogallol.

Fig. 3. Correlation of stabilities of the ligands with lanthanones (▲) MA, (●) TMA, (Δ) aspartic acid and (O) protocatachuic acid.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of the ligands and trivalent lanthanone(III) ions with oxy, thio, amino acids and aromatic phenols were calculated. The potentiometric titration of perchloric

*Present address : Department of Chemistry, North Gujarat University, Patan-384 265.

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND AND BINARY METAL-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°, ionic strength(μ) = 0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	pK ₁ ^H	pK ₂ ^H	pK ₃ ^H	La ^{III}		Ce ^{III}		Pr ^{III}		Nd ^{III}		Sm ^{III}		Gd ^{III}	
				log k ₁	log k ₂										
				Glycollic acid	10.74	3.47	-	5.54	4.72	5.83	4.85	5.80	4.76	5.35	5.49
Lactic acid	11.12	3.57	-	6.47	4.64	6.32	5.67	6.32	5.54	6.75	5.87	6.63	5.90	6.54	5.93
Malic acid	11.58	4.81	3.19	4.51	4.30	5.23	4.75	5.04	4.52	5.66	5.36	5.42	4.58	6.33	5.39
TGA	10.39	3.39	-	6.00	5.21	5.96	5.16	6.08	5.33	5.87	4.81	6.04	5.47	6.17	5.90
TLA	10.40	3.44	-	5.57	5.17	5.99	5.24	6.24	5.64	6.36	5.62	6.69	5.75	6.67	6.09
TMA	10.54	4.40	2.96	6.13	5.41	6.29	5.41	6.07	5.90	6.51	4.82	6.24	5.76	6.32	5.54
Glycine	9.60	2.31	-	4.09	3.49	4.42	3.52	4.40	3.74	4.50	4.12	5.14	4.34	4.64	4.53
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	-	3.76	3.43	4.29	3.49	4.57	4.00	4.80	3.60	5.10	4.09	5.18	4.23
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	-	5.30	5.01	5.72	5.44	5.48	5.00	5.52	4.87	5.89	4.92	5.65	5.22
Catechol	11.30	9.34	-	8.30	-	9.18	-	9.48	-	9.84	-	9.58	-	10.08	-
Pyrogallol	10.77	8.94	-	8.85	-	9.75	-	9.75	-	10.42	-	10.15	-	10.05	-
Protocatechuic acid	12.25	8.97	4.43	9.28	-	10.08	-	10.18	-	11.41	-	10.48	-	10.68	-

Minimum deviation = ± 0.05 units.

acid, perchloric acid + ligand and perchloric acid + ligand + metal were carried out against carbonate-free standard sodium hydroxide. The data of proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants are presented in Table 1. The corresponding coordinating tendencies are shown in Figs. 1-3. The order of the formation constants for the binary oxy, thio, amino acids and aromatic phenol systems are as follows : glycollic acid < lactic acid > malic acid, thioglycollic acid $\approx$ thiolactic acid < thiomalic acid, glycine = α -alanine < aspartic acid and protocatechuic acid < catechol < pyrogallol. The order⁷ of the coordinating tendencies of the above four series is as follows : aromatic phenols > oxy acids $\approx$ thio acids > amino acids. In addition to the formation constants and coordinating tendencies of the above four series. The stability of the trivalent lanthanone with GA, TGA, glycine and catechol follows the order : La < Ce $\approx$ Pr < Nd > Sm < Gd; La $\approx$ Ce < Pr > Nd < Sm < Gd; La < Ce $\approx$ Pr < Nd < Sm > Gd and La < Ce < Pr < Nd > Sm < Gd respectively. The above formation constant orders of all the ligands and series have been explained in terms of their structures and basicities⁸. Besides, the size of the metal ion and ionic potential are two important factors in deciding the value of formation constants.

The proton-ligand formation constants of aromatic phenols are higher compared to amino acids, hence, it is obvious that aromatic phenol forms more stable

complexes. The more electronegative coordinating oxygen atom and trivalent lanthanide ion experience more interaction resulting in the formation of highly stable complexes. In addition, due to the presence of resonance effect in aromatic phenol, ring delocalised π -orbitals also play an important role in binding of the ligand. Thus M-O bond becomes more stronger in aromatic phenols. From the proton-ligand stability constant values of oxy acids it is expected that their formation constant should be higher than the corresponding thio acids. But the formation constant values of oxy and thio acids are nearly the same. The charge transfer into continuum orbitals of sulphur is more probable than the charge transfer to the orbitals of oxygen. Sulphur have vacant *d*-orbitals which can be used for *d* π -*p* π bonding. These two factors are responsible for higher values of formation constants of thio acids. The proton-ligand constant of malic acid is higher than that of glycollic and lactic acid. It acts as tridentate ligand. It forms less stable complexes than glycollic acid and lactic acid. This is due to bigger size of the malic acid molecule, creating steric hindrance which alter the stability of the malic acid complexes. TGA and TLA are bidentate while TMA is tridentate, coordination being from SH and COOH groups.

The calculated metal-ligand formation constant values are in agreement with the proton-ligand formation constants of the amino acids. The basicity of the

glycine and α -alanine is nearly the same. Hence their tendencies to form complexes should be the same. The effective basicity of aspartate ion is more than glycine and α -alanine, hence it forms more stable complexes. Amino acid anion has one negative charge in glycine and α -alanine, while aspartate ion has got two negative charge. Therefore, interaction of amino acid anion with lanthanone(III) ion is comparatively less than the corresponding oxy and thio acid anions. This results in lowering of the formation constants value of the amino acids.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. The metal nitrates solutions of desired concentrations were prepared from the higher molar stock solutions. Free perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and metal nitrates were standardised by acid-base⁹ and complexometric¹⁰ methods. The proton-ligand and binary metal-ligand formation constants were determined in aqueous media at $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO_4) and $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using Irving-Rossotti^{11,12} titration technique. A 1 : 10 ratio of M : L was used for the equilibrium study. Nitrogen gas was used to create inert atmosphere. The pH measurement were carried out with a Control Dynamics pH meter fitted with a combination glass electrode assembly.

The values of proton-ligand stability constants $\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$, $\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{p}K_3^{\text{H}}$ and metal-ligand formation constants of binary mono (1 : 1) and bis (1 : 2) M(III)-L complexes were calculated from the potentiometric titration data using Rossotti-Rossotti technique¹³. The least-squares¹¹ method was used to get the refined value of formation constants.

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